

Open resilience: Building infrastructure together (ORBIT) landscape scan

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Introduction

Funding for open infrastructure (OI) in the domains of scholarly communication and open science is often one-off, project-based, and institutionally siloed, which can discourage long-term planning and shared responsibility. There is little coordinated investment strategy in this ecosystem, despite overlapping dependencies. This can foster a survivalist mindset among projects and discourage long-term collaboration.

This landscape scan investigates recent strategic ideation and activity among US-based academic library consortia with respect to their investment in and adoption of OI.¹ The purpose of this analysis is to identify areas of alignment, activity, and opportunity for collective action in support of open scholarly infrastructure. This work was undertaken by Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) as part of its broader mission to facilitate sustainable, community-led infrastructure for open knowledge.

Methods

IOI conducted a targeted review of strategic plans as well as public presentations, news releases, and other relevant materials published within the past 12 months by a convenience sample of US-based library consortia (see [Appendix A: List of Strategic Planning Documents Analyzed](#)). The analysis focused on identifying (1) explicit references to open infrastructure investments, (2) emergent themes across organizational strategies, and (3) concrete examples of consortial engagement with OI. The goal was to assess current trends and surface potential areas of synergy and opportunity for future collaboration and investment. Other library consortia support for “open,” for example in subscribe-to-open models and similar initiatives, are included in this analysis only where they overlap with explicit support for OI.

Concurrently with our desk research, IOI conducted 12 interviews with leaders of US-based library consortia and related organizations/communities in July and August, 2025, to understand and document how current political, social, and economic pressure points are changing the constellation of players and their strategies for survival (see [Appendix B: List of Interviewees](#) and [Appendix C: Semi-Structured Interview Protocol](#)).

¹ IOI originally intended to undertake this study with funding from the Institute of Museum of Library Services (IMLS); we therefore limited our scope to US-based organizations.

Interviews touched on topics including:

- Current strategic goals and plans;
- Current and desired support for OI within their business model;
- Forecasting potential “worst-case scenarios” and responses;
- Intersections with other consortia, from informal relationships to true collective action/strategy;
- Appetite for collective approaches, such as shared staffing and infrastructure;
- Changing marketplace for consortia, especially as the content licensing environment evolves.

Findings

US-based library consortia provide an essential collaborative framework that enables academic institutions to achieve preservation, access, innovation, and educational goals that would be impossible individually. Many have acted as community hubs and provided core services to members for decades. Despite their longstanding contributions and proven value, these consortial networks find themselves at a critical juncture. As one consortium leader observed, the “status quo is becoming unsustainable” as external forces such as increasing vendor consolidation, fiscal austerity, and a capacity crisis within individual institutions put libraries and library workers under untenable pressure. Some consortial leaders see potential for more radical change in this environment (both in terms of shifts in the missions of consortia as well as in the power dynamics of the research and scholarly communication landscape at large), though this is tempered by institutional conservatism and “wait and see” mentalities among their members.

An overarching theme of our conversations with library consortium leaders was **interdependence**, a growing need to leverage collaborative models to increase resilience and capability while managing costs. There's emerging recognition that consortia themselves need to coordinate more systematically, moving toward a “network of networks” model where individual consortia specialize in their strengths while working collectively for greater impact, resilience, and distribution of risk.

The following sections provide an overview of themes that emerged from our desk research and from conversations with consortium leaders about their evolving strategies, the risks and challenges they face, and their core value propositions.

In an era of unprecedented financial insecurity for US academic institutions, library consortia may act as critical bulwarks against resource scarcity and service disruption.

Providing a safety net

The anticipated loss of federal funding support, particularly Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS) funding, represents an existential threat for US libraries. Consortium leaders are paying close attention. One expects a shortfall of six million dollars in statewide library funding; another anticipates over nine million dollars in cuts to their state; and yet another reported 25% budget cuts at some member institutions, each due to the defunding of the IMLS. This comes at a time when, consortium leaders told us, libraries are already suffering from previous workforce reductions that have forced them to rely more and more on vended services, some of which charge “exorbitant” pricing. Libraries are looking to consortia, long-time allies, to replace this lost internal capacity and help them control costs. The broader concern is that the dramatic shifts in federal and other funding sources mean that “many of the supports that our community relies on are absent.” Consortia are trying to fill these gaps with diminishing resources. Consortium leaders expressed an urgent commitment to helping member libraries manage costs through automation, shared services, and collective licensing negotiations.

Many of the strategic plans we analyzed (all published prior to federal funding changes) emphasized the need to grow membership and identify new revenue streams in order to maintain or improve sustainability. Although the leaders we spoke with reported that they are not currently experiencing anything close to “worst case scenarios” in member retention, they are still bracing for dropped memberships and preparing financial contingency plans based on federal funding cuts, reductions in international student enrollment, and other pressures. There is widespread worry about the “enrollment cliff,” budget cuts, and members entering “lifeboat mode” where they must choose which essential services to retain. Some consortia are modeling scenarios where a percentage of their member institutions might close entirely.

In an era of unprecedented financial insecurity for US academic institutions, library consortia may act as critical bulwarks against resource scarcity and service disruption. Several of the consortial leaders we interviewed view themselves as providing a safety net for libraries that are “struggling to maintain their services,” or facing “drastic funding cuts,” even if it means taking on a level of financial risk or dipping into consortial reserves. This stance reflects a growing understanding that individual library survival depends on ecosystem-wide resilience. As Courtney Mumma, Texas Digital Library (TDL) Deputy

Director, explained, "I don't really see any other way forward other than sharing infrastructure and sharing expertise in the way that we do as we see resources of all kinds being stripped from institutions."

Cultivating mission-driven communities

Jacob Nadal, Executive Director of the Center for Research Libraries (CRL) reminds members that, though they provide shared services, CRL is not a vendor. Nadal commented, "Metaphorically, I think of us as a joint venture, a joint stock company to accomplish certain purposes." Mark Sullivan, Executive Director of Information Delivery Services (IDS) Network, describes the initiative he leads as a resource-sharing cooperative, "a group of individuals volunteering their time to build for a better future."

Consortium leaders further emphasized their roles as **convener, coordinator, connector, and strategist**. They bring together staff at institutions that might otherwise not interact, provide them with field-level intelligence and guidance, and help them to identify opportunities to work at scale. For Charlie Barlow, Executive Director of the Boston Library Consortium (BLC), "The best thing we can do to respond to risks is to serve as a convener of ideas and thinking. Set the table for collaboration." Kirsten Leonard, Executive Director of the Private Academic Library Network of Indiana (PALNI), described members' reliance on the consortium to take on emerging issues: "Any new challenge in particular, members want PALNI to take it on because local capacity isn't there." Many described building and supporting community-building within the membership as a core strategy. Isaac Gilman, Executive Director of the Orbis Cascade Alliance described a core role for the consortium as "positioning our libraries to be empowered to collaborate in the ways they want to." The benefits of this mission-driven work of consortia may extend beyond the membership. As CRL's Nadal explains, "The club is exclusive, but the work doesn't have to be exclusive."

Still, consortia and similar organizations need to be able to make a strong business case for new investments of time and money. Several emphasized that their consortia do not invest in OI for purely altruistic purposes. Rather, they carefully evaluate new investments and renewals using formal or informal frameworks designed to gauge total costs (and potential savings) and demonstrate alignment with concrete needs. The activities that garner the most support and accolades among BLC members, according to Barlow, are those that bring "visible, tangible, quantifiable return on their investment." Kate McCready, Program Director for Open Publishing in the Center for Library Programs at the Big Ten Academic Alliance (BTAA) emphasizes that investments "have to benefit our members. Our members want to see institutional engagement in it in some way, shape, or form. They're not able to be altruistic grantmakers, they are tasked with supporting their institutions." When evaluating potential investments, BTAA has "a lot of very concrete things that we're looking for," she says.

Even a core service like preservation needs to “anchor its value in the present,” says Nadal of CRL. “We have to reassure people that we have a good preservation plan that’s naturally integrated with a present-tense value proposition.” Leaders described balancing near-term cost savings with potential long-term sustainability. **Even if a vended solution appears less expensive at the outset, an open source investment may pay off over time, by allowing consortia to build added-value offerings that serve members and generate revenue and by avoiding vendor lock-in.** Leonard (PALNI) explains, “The whole purpose of moving to open is flexibility in business and service models.” One leader mentioned a need for more precise tools for measuring this type of longer-term return on investment (ROI).

By convening communities, providing shared services, and strengthening member capacity, consortia ensure that investments in open infrastructure are driven by collective needs, not just market pressures. This alignment gives libraries not only better tools, but also a stronger voice in shaping the systems they depend on. The alternative is to cede control to providers of proprietary software, whose primary obligation is often to their shareholders, not scholarship. Consortia can lead the way for libraries to invest in sustainable, equitable, and community-governed infrastructure by acting as conveners and capacity-builders, not just service-providers. They can also serve as bridges connecting libraries to open solutions instead of proprietary environments.

Building resilient open infrastructure models

Sustainable open infrastructure requires more than just adopting open source software — it demands active participation in interconnected communities that distribute both development responsibilities and operational risks across multiple stakeholders. Kristi Park, Executive Director of the Texas Digital Library (TDL) described the consortium’s active participation in the governance of DSpace, a critical infrastructure for their members, so that “it becomes a stronger system and it becomes harder for it to fail.”

In a constricted fiscal environment, it can seem compelling for institutions to go with proprietary services due to the relative ease of procurement, set-up, and maintenance, and the convenience of vertical integration. However, consortium leaders emphasized the risks of this approach and described hard-learned lessons about vendor consolidation and market failure.

Several leaders mentioned “a growing desire to not be locked in to basically two large vendors and use our position and leverage to push back harder.” Pricing for one key service that enables collaborative collection development and stewardship “has gotten

exorbitant and out-of-reach for many smaller members,” according to one leader we spoke to. They are hoping collaborative open source solutions already in development may provide a viable replacement for this and other proprietary systems in the future.

Consortium leaders also provided firsthand accounts of how dependency on single providers creates systemic vulnerabilities, particularly in specialized markets. For communities relying on niche proprietary software vendors, the interest in open source is often a risk management strategy rather than an ideological imperative. As Nadal recounted, “There's a certain risk with proprietary software that the provider will change their rates, go out of business. So open source has a risk management value.”

Barak Zahavy, Assistant Director of the Research Collections and Preservation Consortium (ReCAP), gave the example of inventory management software for high-density storage facilities. Of around 100 such facilities that exist in North America, a large proportion have adopted software from the one remaining vendor in the space, which has outlasted its only major competitor. As Zahavy describes, “It's a tiny software vendor and there's a lot of concern that they'll end up just like the one that went out of business.”

Individual libraries have “fewer and fewer resources to devote to their own infrastructures” due to staffing cuts, according to several leaders we spoke with. This is creating an opportunity for consortia to offer their members new models of pooled staffing and technology. Interviewees shared their hopes that interconsortium collaboration on major open infrastructure projects could build the necessary capacity, redundancy, shared expertise, and long-term commitment that rivals proprietary vendor relationships.

The end goal is a robust ecosystem where the withdrawal of any individual component — whether a company, a single institution, or even a consortium — doesn't threaten the broader network's stability.

Embracing interoperability

Library consortia occupy a unique position in the information ecosystem; many serve as bridges between heterogeneous institutional partners, spanning research-intensive universities, small liberal arts colleges, land grant institutions, and even public libraries. The diversity of their stakeholders creates a powerful incentive for consortia to champion interoperability as a foundation for effective collaboration.

Consortia play a key role as stewards of the scholarly record, extending beyond individual institutional needs to serve broader scholarly and cultural preservation goals. Coordinated

collection development supports the fundamental academic activities of teaching, learning, and research. Shared collections remain the foundational service for the vast majority of the consortia we spoke with; phrases like “removing barriers,” providing “equitable access,” or enabling “cost-effective and sustainable access” figure in most of their mission statements. Maurice York, Director of Library Programs at the Big Ten Academic Alliance (BTAA) describes one of the consortium’s guiding principles as “public knowledge for the public good.” There’s a strong focus on leveraging collective buying power (which can represent over a billion dollars annually for the largest consortia), avoiding duplication across member institutions, and facilitating access to the scholarly record.

Consortia are also grappling with new political realities including, among other concerns, “strict rules around and against DEI” and “harmful and obscene content to minors regulations,” as well as the loss or corruption of government-held data. There’s fear that digital collections might be targeted for censorship, leading to conversations about how to “best mitigate risk to collections being destroyed” through diversified preservation strategies. The current financial crisis in higher education also poses risks to physical collections. To counteract this, PALNI aims to establish a memorandum of understanding and a process for transferring scarce collection materials from an at-risk school to another PALNI institution or a party capable of retaining and providing access to these materials for the scholarly community. PALNI is also considering how to work together to manage interlibrary loan and collections more effectively for schools that have rich collections but fewer staff.

Open infrastructure tends to support and align with open standards and practices that facilitate metadata exchange and integrations with third party systems, making it a natural choice for consortia looking to advance interoperability. As Jill Morris, Executive Director of the Partnership for Academic Library Collaboration and Innovation (PALCI), articulated, “open infrastructure is a strategy that we’re applying in order to support a high degree of interoperability across our institutions ... and combat some of the tendencies where libraries get stuck in one vendor path, or one vertical that then prevents them from being able to work with other organizations that have made a different choice.”

Opportunities for collective action

Collaborative investment in OI serves the stated goals of consortia, namely **managing risk, supporting interoperability, containing long-term costs for members, and providing equitable access to knowledge**. It can also provide new revenue generation opportunities for consortia, who can provide member benefits by hosting infrastructure, facilitating consortial memberships, and offering OI-related professional development opportunities, among other possibilities. The most promising opportunities are those that help consortia build on existing strengths while shielding them from mission-creep or overextension. Based on the findings from our interviews and desk research, as well as examples of current consortial engagement with OI, we propose the following areas as high-potential avenues for collaborative investment: hosting, building, sponsoring, training, and cultivating.

Hosting: Leveraging scale

A number of the consortia we interviewed already host infrastructure that enables open content production and distribution as part of their mission to provide broad and equitable access to content for their members and researchers at large.

Hosting shared infrastructure such as digital repositories, integrated library systems (ILS), open publishing software, and digital preservation environments. For example:

- TDL currently hosts a [digital repository](#) and the [Texas Data Repository](#) and [operates an Open Journal Systems \(OJS\) hosting service](#).
- TDL has also [partnered with the Portico digital preservation service](#) and the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) to host a Portico archive replica using TACC's storage.
- PALNI and PALCI host the [Hyku for consortia](#) project² (with participants like [VIVA](#))
- Via the [PALNI Open Press](#), PALNI offers OJS, Pressbooks, Hyku, and Omeka to 20+ institutions.
- VIVA runs [Pressbooks](#) for open textbook publishing.
- BTAA piloted [Meru](#) as a platform for consortial publishing.

² Leonard, K., Reed, M., & Trinoskey, J. (2025). The Power of PALNI's Deep Collaboration. *Journal of Library Administration*, 65(5), 616–626. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2025.2506152>

- PALNI coordinated an ILS migration for members in 2014.³
- Orbis Cascade Alliance hosts an [archival finding aid database](#) built on an [open source code base](#).

Building on this momentum, deeper collaboration across consortia could amplify the collective impact of US libraries in advancing open access, scholarly communication, and open science.

Collaborate on hosting shared OI. Shared hosting arrangements allow consortia to take advantage of economies of scale. Instead of each consortium — or worse, each individual library — investing in redundant technical expertise, servers, and maintenance contracts, groups of consortia can pool resources to run robust, professionally managed instances of key OIs. This could take the form of multi-consortium hosting centers for widely used tools such as DSpace, Samvera, or Open Journal Systems (OJS). For instance, one consortium might specialize in repository hosting while another could take responsibility for publishing platforms, creating a complementary network of services that collectively cover the major components of open scholarship infrastructure. Such specialization would reduce duplication, leverage economies of scale, and build deeper expertise in particular platforms.

Participate in OI communities. Sustaining open-source platforms requires more than financial investment — it also depends on active community participation. Interconsortium partnerships could enable libraries to jointly plan development roadmaps; contribute code, documentation, training, and support; test new features; and participate in governance bodies. For example, a consortium with strong software development expertise might lead code contributions to a shared platform, while another consortium could focus on user support or community engagement. Such a division of labor would help distribute responsibilities more equitably across the library community, making it easier for smaller institutions to participate meaningfully without being overwhelmed by resource constraints. By pooling investments of time, staff expertise, and financial resources into common open-source infrastructures, consortia could improve the long-term stability and scalability of these tools. For example, a coordinated approach to feature development, security updates, and documentation could reduce duplication of effort across institutions while ensuring a more reliable user experience for libraries and researchers nationwide.

OIs that support the creation, distribution, discovery, and preservation of open content represent some of the most promising areas for the hosting approach because they are a natural extension of what consortia already do best.

³ Leonard, Reed, and Trinoskey, 2025

These systems *align directly with the core missions* of US-based consortia and their members: ensuring broad, equitable access to knowledge, reducing reliance on costly commercial platforms, and preserving the scholarly record for the long term. Melanie Schlosser, Senior Community Facilitator at Educopia and Community Facilitator for the Library Publishing Coalition sees significant potential for consortia to support library publishing and develop economies of scale for members.

Hosting infrastructure in these areas also *delivers clear financial and operational advantages*. By working together, consortia can leverage economies of scale: spreading costs, consolidating expertise, and creating more reliable and resilient services than any single consortium or institution could maintain alone. Just as importantly, OIs open the door to new revenue generation opportunities. **Hosting (and added-value offerings such as user support and training) can be structured to give consortia a stronger financial footing while delivering tangible value back to members.**

When strategically bundled, these services could even evolve into a *vertically integrated suite* covering the entire scholarly communication lifecycle — from journal publishing with Open Journal Systems or Janeway, to repository hosting with DSpace or Samvera, to long-term preservation through LOCKSS or comparable systems. The tools already exist, and they are proven, trusted, and community-driven.

Building: Countering market consolidation

Developing or adapting open-source tools often becomes essential in areas where commercial options fall short. This can happen when the needs are highly specialized, such as software for managing high-density storage inventory, or when the marketplace is dominated by one or two vendors whose pricing models put the tools out of reach for many institutions. As Gilman from Orbis Cascade explained, “We’re constantly watching for situations where our libraries feel boxed in — where there’s only one option and institutions are forced to ‘pay the piper.’ Those are exactly the areas where we try to step in and see how much influence we can exert to create better alternatives.”

Consortium leaders described their participation in numerous technology development projects, many of which address needs related to collaborative print and digital collection development, an area heavily impacted by market consolidation. Examples include:

- the [OpenRS](#) initiative, which brings together library consortia and key vendors to invest in and adopt open source middleware to facilitate resource sharing;
- [CrossLink](#) from the IDS Network, which supports interlibrary loan and sharing activities by facilitating cross-catalog discovery; and

- the [ReShare Community](#)'s cross-sector collaboration to improve controlled digital lending and other resource sharing activities by developing a suite of open source tools.

OIs that support resource sharing, interoperability, open metadata, and inventory management represent some of the most promising areas for the building approach because they are mission-critical tools in areas where consortia have identified high levels of risk or frustration with existing options.

Genya O’Gara Director of the Virtual Library of Virginia (VIVA) notes that the consortium supports a “deep resource-sharing network that is looking for innovative ways to move in a new direction.” Member institutions have been closely watching emerging open source projects “and would be willing to put a lot of their capital and funds behind making something else happen because they’re so dissatisfied with the current space.”

Projects like CrossLink exemplify this approach, using open standards and linked data to connect multiple resource sharing systems rather than relying on proprietary applications that tend to silo metadata and content. Increased coordination among consortia in the following areas aligns well with the needs consortium leaders reported:

- Middleware or standards that improve interoperability⁴ as well as open metadata initiatives that help reduce reliance on vendors for information exchange, retention planning, and collections analysis.
- Metadata aggregation and discovery systems, including integrated library systems (ILS) and resource sharing systems⁵ that help libraries to connect researchers with materials held by different institutions.
- Collections analysis tools and the open data that supports them. Tina Baich of the Eastern Academic Scholars' Trust (EAST) describes one of the consortium’s primary goals as finding “a way to make the information that will help people make decisions about print collections more readily available to them.” Other leaders mentioned plans to implement collections analysis services to advance shared collections activities and help libraries realize cost savings.

⁴ See, for example the [OpenRS](#) initiative, which has involved several library consortia in investing in and adopting an open source middleware to facilitate resource sharing; [CrossLink](#) from the IDS Network; and ISO 18626, a protocol for peer-to-peer resource sharing requests.

⁵ See, for example, the [ReShare Community](#), an active cross-sector collaboration that aims to improve interlibrary resource sharing.

Sponsoring: Aligning funding and membership commitments

Some of the most impactful ways consortia can support OI do not require building or hosting systems directly, but rather ensuring the financial sustainability of existing community-driven platforms. Third-party services such as the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), the Open Library of Humanities (OLH), or arXiv are foundational to the global research ecosystem, yet they rely heavily on voluntary contributions that are often fragmented and unpredictable. Coordinated consortial sponsorship offers a way to strengthen these critical services while amplifying the collective influence of libraries in shaping their future.

Many consortia we spoke to already contribute to such services. For example:

- In 2024, Ivy Plus Libraries Confederation announced a [financial commitment to the Center for Open Science's OSF Preprints platform](#)
- BTAA provides [consortial funding for arXiv](#)
- BLC, PASCAL, BTAA, Orbis Cascade Alliance, and others fund [the Directory of Open Access Journals \(DOAJ\)](#)
- BTAA also channels [consortial investments to the Directory of Open Access Books \(DOAB\) and OAPEN, the Open Library of of the Humanities \(OLH\), and OA Switchboard](#)

Consortia could maximize their impact by aligning funding commitments, thereby channeling greater and more predictable financial support to the most mission-critical initiatives. Beyond sustaining these services, a coordinated financial strategy would also give libraries a stronger collective voice in shaping the direction and governance of the infrastructures they depend upon. Conversely, coordination could also broaden the group of OIs that consortia are able to support. **Rather than each consortium choosing a handful of services to back in isolation, pooled planning and communication would allow the community to cover a wider spectrum of needs without overburdening individual budgets.** For example, one consortium might take the lead on sustaining humanities-focused platforms such as OLH, while another prioritizes infrastructure for open data.

Another powerful mechanism to support OI is leveraging consortial scale to negotiate memberships with OI providers, particularly those that facilitate essential services such as data sharing and persistent identifiers. For example, GWLA has launched a [consortial membership with Dryad](#) and PALNI's [Crossref and Datacite memberships](#) provide DOIs for scholarly content created by faculty, students, and staff across its member institutions. These memberships make valuable services broadly available with less administrative burden for individual libraries.

In some cases, consortial memberships are the most practical way to meet emerging needs. Data repositories are a good example: while some consortium leaders reported growing interest among member libraries, the demand is not yet strong enough to justify building or hosting infrastructure independently. Here, consortia could play a crucial role by offering access to trusted external solutions with minimal overhead, meeting member needs today while keeping options open for deeper investment as demand evolves.

Training: Professional development and community-of-practice

Consortia have long served as hubs for professional development and capacity building, helping their member institutions strengthen expertise while avoiding duplication of effort. Many include “empowering members,” “building capacity,” and “developing leaders” in their mission statements and strategic priorities.

This role is becoming more urgent as libraries lose institutional knowledge and internal capacity. As Gilman (Orbis Cascade) observed, training needs have rapidly shifted in the last few years: once focused on how to use consortium-provided services, there is increasing demand for foundational library skills as staff expertise in e-resources, systems, and related areas erodes through loss of positions. In response, Gilman’s staff has been “developing more of a back-to-basics or 101 training series in certain areas to help try and address that need.”

Training connected to OI represents an especially promising opportunity. By embedding OI awareness and skills into professional development programs, consortia can help librarians both deepen their current expertise and acquire entirely new competencies. As Gilman explained, “open infrastructure, really, is one of the ways that we feel like we can have some influence, we can help to shape the industry and that ecosystem more broadly ... we’ve identified this as being one of the only ways where we get to have a voice in reclaiming some of that power and that sense of agency for our institutions, for a sharing-centered network.” Training is thus not only about skills development, but also about equipping librarians to participate in — and shape — the broader open ecosystem.

Partnerships with OI providers offer an opportunity to deepen this role through joint training opportunities, credentialing, or ambassadorship programs that could not only generate revenue, but also promote awareness of OI and support the consortium’s broader strategic goals. Interconsortium collaboration on training programs could allow consortia to build internal expertise in certain areas while allowing their members to benefit from a wide range of knowledge within other consortia.

Cultivating: Shared governance and project administration

Jill Morris (PALCI) noted that many consortium-led initiatives are “duplicating the work of project-level administration and governance administration.” She sees an opportunity to distribute this overhead across aligned projects, allowing initiatives to scale more effectively. PALCI already demonstrates one model: hosting staff on behalf of the Greater Western Library Alliance (GWLA), with some individuals working across projects for both organizations. Similarly, Anne Craig, outgoing Executive Director at the Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Illinois (CARLI), pointed out that shared staffing arrangements can be especially useful for advancing one-off, time-limited, or niche projects such as space planning, salary analysis, or specialized cataloging — areas where it would not make sense for each consortium to build permanent in-house expertise. O’Gara (VIVA) would like to see consortia “collectively decide on high priorities and continue momentum as a group,” working to pool resources and work with funders to advance critical projects.

The leaders we spoke to shared examples of successful collaborations, but also underscored persistent challenges. Too often, partnerships rely on “individual expertise and relationships” or informal agreements where a “handshake was enough.” While these ad hoc arrangements can move projects forward, they also create risks: if a key individual leaves or priorities shift, projects can stall or collapse entirely. As one leader put it, there is a growing awareness of the “risk we don’t talk enough about,” ensuring that “projects outlast any one person.” Craig (CARLI) further emphasized the challenge of diffuse leadership: “It’s hard when we try to do things as a consortium and there’s no one in charge, you get to it when you get to it, that’s when things fall apart.”

This points to a clear need for more intentional coordination around project management and administration. Inter-consortium cooperation could play a pivotal role here. By pooling resources, consortia could establish shared administrative structures and governance frameworks that provide consistency and continuity across initiatives. This would not only reduce duplicated effort but also ensure that projects are properly resourced, timelines are managed, and accountability is maintained. As Morris (PALCI) suggested, developing structures or bodies that “help ensure everybody was on the same page as they’re collaborating and co-funding” would go a long way toward stabilizing and professionalizing inter-consortial efforts.

More formalized mechanisms could include shared project management roles, rotating leadership models with clear lines of accountability, or joint funding for dedicated coordinators whose sole responsibility is to manage cross-consortial initiatives. These kinds of investments would enable projects to scale beyond the pilot phase, prevent them from falling through the cracks when staff move on, and make them more attractive to external partners or funders who look for evidence of long-term stability.

Risk aversion and institutional inertia could increase long-term vulnerability by preventing necessary adaptations.

Challenges to address

Risk-aversion. The cumulative effect of external pressures, including political, economic, and technological shifts, is creating a more cautious environment where “people are a little more risk-averse.” One leader described “a wait-and-see-mentality among our board, some might say head in the sand, some might say cautious optimism,” and a lack of appetite “to do things in any meaningfully different way.” Consortium leaders also confront the need to provide “big, impactful savings and cost avoidance opportunities for things that [members] need to spend money on, rather than going out and offering them a whole bunch of new stuff.” Another leader described the challenge of “inertia in the midst of chaos,” and the persistent question of how to advance projects “when everything else is burning and people don't have energy for the day-to-day, let alone a culture or technology change.” Paradoxically, risk aversion and institutional inertia could increase long-term vulnerability by preventing necessary adaptations.

Moving from project to community. Many open source projects begin their lives as small projects, driven by a single individual or small group. This provides the agility that new initiatives need to get off the ground, but to remain sustainable and to bring in new users, these projects need to build mature governance models, engagement programs, and revenue streams (and/or volunteer maintainer communities). The leaders we spoke to who run open source projects frequently mentioned the challenge of onboarding new code contributors and recruiting new adopters (e.g., other institutions or consortia who might benefit from using the product). Describing TDL's turnkey electronic thesis and dissertation (ETD) management system, Vireo, Park explained, “I think there's a real challenge with a lot of these projects where the people shepherding them are people like me. They're volunteer efforts by committees. Doing community development work and making it possible for people to contribute and engage takes a lot of effort, a lot of sustained effort.” Zahavy (ReCAP) described a similar dilemma for FETCH, an open source tool for inventory management for high-density library storage facilities, developed by the Library of Congress in collaboration with the broader community. The project partners benefited from Lyrasis' “It Takes a Village” program, but have still found it challenging to build a formal community and governance structure.⁶ As Zahavy recounted, “We have a strong

⁶ <https://itav.lyrasis.org/itav-community-case-study-fetch/>

community and have come a long way, yet I still ask the question, 'How do we demonstrate that this project is worth investing in for everyone?'" There is wide recognition that volunteer-based governance models struggle to provide adequate accountability and professional support to move consortium-built OIs from passion projects to sustainable infrastructure communities.

Scale versus customizability. A persistent challenge for multi-institutional collaboration is the need to address the needs of diverse stakeholders while maintaining systems that are sustainable, easy to use, and scalable. As one consortium leader remarked, "Getting requirements in order and aligned in a consortial environment is challenging because there are differing options, or different perspectives amongst the partners within a consortium."

Restricted capacity at member institutions. As member libraries experience staffing cuts and "experienced staff walk out the door," consortia face downstream consequences of having to provide more support with fewer resources. There's concern about staff burnout and the sustainability of expanded service models, as well as increasing reliance on proprietary infrastructures to replace in-house capacity. This affects the capacity of institutions to engage in open infrastructure projects, even those hosted at the consortium level. Leonard (PALNI) noted that building OI expertise at the consortium level is essential in order to be able to translate that knowledge into simple guidance and workflows for the staff at member institutions who have little to no time to devote to learning the intricacies of new systems. PALNI has put effort into making their infrastructure "as easy to use, as efficient to use as possible." Leonard added, "just because you have a system doesn't mean small schools can use the system."

Calibrating consortial memberships for mutual benefit. It is unclear whether consortial membership pricing (often discounted vis à vis individual membership) provides sufficient revenue for projects and organizations that already operate with low margins, or whether this pricing ends up creating inadvertent financial strain. There is a need for further research into how OIs establish consortial pricing and the factors they take into account, as well as determining estimated return on investment for consortia and individual members in consortial memberships. The Datacite and Crossref membership deals established by PALNI and GWLA's consortial membership with Dryad could serve as interesting case studies. Do consortial memberships save labor in terms of set-up or maintenance versus memberships with individual institutions? How much savings or overspending do these deals represent for the parties involved? How can we spot and correct when this balance is off?

Deciding where to invest. A number of consortia we spoke to broker direct financial contributions to OI, notably DOAJ and DOAB, though the scale of consortial funding remains low. For example, the Association of Research Libraries (ARL), found that US

institutions (including consortia) have contributed only 13% of the global funding coordinated through the SCOSS (Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services) initiative, which supports a select group of OIs.⁷ Barlow (BLC) noted that it's a "very tough ask in the current environment for an organization to voluntarily make an investment when they could sit back and hope others will step forward." Park (TDL) invoked the "proliferation of applications and communities" and the challenge of "figuring out how to pick, and how to shore up the things that are already the most sustainable and useful within the community is a really important part of the process. And be willing to let go of some things." Some consortium leaders rely on specific criteria or rubrics to evaluate infrastructure investments. These tools consider factors ranging from values alignment (e.g., prioritizing academy-owned solutions) to more pragmatic considerations (e.g., supported standards). Winning investments meet concrete needs while ideally advancing a community benefit. Consortium leaders told us that current rubrics can fall short when evaluating OI and specifically expressed a need for better tools to evaluate total cost of adoption. Consortium leaders also told us that they did not have a comprehensive understanding of the infrastructure their members currently engage with (or would like to engage with), making it difficult to identify potential synergies.

Conclusion

The findings from this landscape scan make clear that US-based library consortia can occupy a pivotal position in advancing sustainable, community-led open infrastructure. Faced with growing financial pressures, vendor consolidation, and shrinking institutional capacity, consortia are increasingly called upon to act not only as service providers, but also as conveners, capacity-builders, and advocates for collective resilience. Their ability to balance near-term value for members with long-term investments in open, interoperable, and community-governed systems is critical to the success of academic and research libraries in the United States.

Opportunities for collective action, whether through hosting, building, sponsoring, training, or cultivating, demonstrate how shared investments in OI can reduce duplication, expand impact, and reinforce a network of networks model where consortia specialize in their strengths while collaborating for greater scale and influence. At the same time, challenges such as risk-aversion, limited staff capacity, and fragmented funding highlight the need for stronger coordination, professionalized project administration, and more robust tools for evaluating investments.

⁷ <https://www.arl.org/blog/scoss-2021-update-library-consortia-create-path-for-funding-open-infrastructure/>

Ultimately, sustaining open knowledge requires the alignment of diverse communities, each contributing their unique strengths to a shared ecosystem. As Maurice York (BTAA) reminds us, achieving open knowledge “isn’t a question of making all of the consortia look and act the same,” but rather of understanding “what are each of our strengths?” By leveraging those strengths collaboratively, consortia can chart a path toward resilient, equitable, and mission-driven infrastructure that serves not just their members, but the scholarly community and the public good.

Appendix A: List of strategic planning documents analyzed

- Association of Southeastern Research Libraries (ASERL)
[ASERL Ahead - 2027](#)
- Boston Library Consortium (BLC)
[Empowering Libraries: BLC Strategic Action Plan \(PDF\)](#) (2023)
- CARLI (Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Illinois)
[CARLI 2023 Strategic Plan \(PDF\)](#)
- Eastern Academic Scholars' Trust (EAST)
[EAST Strategic Directions 2022–2025 \(PDF\)](#)
- Greater Western Library Alliance (GWLA)
[Vision & Strategic Focus](#) (2019)
- HBCU Library Alliance
[Strategic Plan 2018–2023](#)
- Ivy Plus Libraries Confederation
[Strategic Priorities](#)
- Orbis Cascade Alliance
[Strategic Plan FY2024-26](#)
- PALCI (Partnership for Academic Library Collaboration & Innovation)
[Strategic Outline](#)
- PALNI (Private Academic Library Network of Indiana)
[Strategic Framework 2024–2027](#)
- SCEL (Statewide California Electronic Library Consortium)
[Strategic Pillars](#) (2024)
- Texas Digital Library (TDL)
[Strategic Plan 2020–2023](#) and [TDL Strategic Directions 2025-27](#)
- California Digital Library (CDL)
[Pathways to Open Access](#)

Appendix B: List of interviewees

- **Tina Baich**, Eastern Academic Scholars' Trust (EAST)
- **Charlie Barlow**, Boston Library Consortium
- **Anne Craig**, Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Illinois (CARLI)
- **Isaac Gilman**, Orbis Cascade Alliance
- **Kirsten Leonard**, Private Academic Library Network of Indiana (PALNI)
- **Kate McCready**, Big Ten Academic Alliance (BTAA)
- **Jill Morris**, Partnership for Academic Library Collaboration and Innovation (PALCI)
- **Courtney Mumma**, Texas Digital Library (TDL)
- **Jacob Nadal**, Center for Research Libraries (CRL)
- **Kristi Park**, Texas Digital Library (TDL)
- **Genya O'Gara**, Virtual Library of Virginia, Virtual Library of Virginia (VIVA)
- **Melanie Schlosser**, Library Publishing Coalition
- **Mark Sullivan**, Information Delivery Services (IDS) Network
- **Maurice York**, Big Ten Academic Alliance (BTAA)
- **Barak Zahavy**, Research Collections and Preservation Consortium (ReCAP)

Appendix C:

Semi-structured interview protocol

1. Can you give a brief description of your role and the consortium you represent?
2. What are the current strategic priorities or initiatives for your consortium?
 - a. Have those shifted recently in response to broader sector changes?
 - b. Do any of these relate to supporting open? (eg open access, open science, open data, open infrastructure)
3. Do you see the role of consortia evolving as the marketplace changes, particularly as more content licensing moves toward read and publish agreements and bundled services? If yes, in what ways?
 - a. Are you seeing increased pressure to shift toward service-based or infrastructure-based offerings? If so, from where (e.g., members, vendors, institutions)?
4. What risks are top-of-mind for you and your members given the current fiscal and political climate? Are there any of these actually happening (i.e. not just worst-case-scenarios)?
 - a. How is your consortium preparing for those scenarios, if at all? (E.g., diversification, exit strategies, contingency planning.)
5. How does open infrastructure fit into your future strategic plans?
 - a. In what ways is open infrastructure currently supported, or not, within your consortial business model? This might include hosted infrastructure offerings, consortial memberships, direct funding, in-kind staffing/support, external grants.
 - b. Ideally, what kind of support (financial, staffing, technical) would your consortium like to offer to open infrastructure initiatives?
 - c. Do you face or anticipate any barriers to this kind of support?
 - d. Are there specific open infrastructure initiatives you would like to support, but haven't figured out how to go about it?
6. What kind of relationships do you currently have with other consortia — formal, informal, or strategic?
 - a. Are there any examples of successful joint efforts (e.g., shared services, collective negotiation, co-funding)?
 - b. What made those efforts work (or not)?

7. Are there shared or collective approaches that would interest your consortium going forward? E.g., shared infrastructure, pooled staffing, federated governance.
 - a. Do you have any historical examples of these we can draw from?
8. Is there anything else you would like to share with us about opportunities or challenges for collective investment in open infrastructure?

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